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Человек в цифровой среде: эволюция сознания

Аннотация. В статье анализируются трансформирующие воздействия цифровых технологий на индивидуальное и социальное сознание современного человека. Особое внимание уделяется концепции «двойного взросления», которая подразумевает, что молодые люди сталкиваются не только с традиционными вызовами подросткового возраста, но и с необходимостью формирования своих онлайн-идентичностей в цифровом пространстве. Также обсуждается вопрос, как технологические новшества изменили восприятие пространства и коммуникации, предоставляя возможности для глобального взаимодействия, одновременно порождая ряд серьезных проблем. Рассматриваются последствия появившейся возможности быстрого обмена информацией для процессов самоанализа и управления временем. В то же время, подчеркивается, что осознанное использование цифровых инструментов может способствовать личностному росту и улучшению общего благополучия.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, осознанность, рефлексия, мобильные приложения.

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Human in the digital environment: the evolution of consciousness

Abstract. The article analyzes the transformative impact of digital technologies on the individual and social consciousness of contemporary humans. Particular attention is paid to the concept of «double growing up», which implies that young people face not only the traditional challenges of adolescence, but also the need to form their online identities in the digital world. It also discusses how technological innovations have changed the perception of space and communication, providing opportunities for global interaction, while simultaneously giving rise to a number of serious problems. The implications of the emerging opportunity for rapid information exchange for the processes of self-analysis and time management are considered. At the same time, it is emphasized that the conscious use of digital tools can contribute to personal growth and improve overall well-being.

Key words: digitalization, mindfulness, reflection, mobile applications.

In the modern world, almost every person is a «cyborg» [4; 8]. Cyborgization is a process associated with the symbiosis of a man and technology, the emergence of a special kind of a «biotechnical» man, as well as the creation of robots connected to artificial intelligence, and, as a consequence, a change in the technical reality into which humanity is joining at an accelerated pace, and within which modern people are forced to exist [5]. Non-traditional anthropology believes that with the development of digital technologies, people have turned into a new form of *Homo sapiens* [1].

In this regard, it is important to understand how technologies influence social and individual consciousness.

Firstly, technology creates an additional stage of growing up. In today's environment, young people have to go through a traditional teenage period, which is difficult in itself. Then they go through a stage of forming their second self in the digital environment, which is getting worse by the existence of a digital trace of their online activities. Just as teenagers explore their personality, values and social roles in real life, they also create and develop their online identity [3; 7]. This includes choosing photos, publications, creating content and interacting with other users on social networks. Online identity differs from real identity in that it is under the user's complete control, which allows them to adjust it at their own discretion. In the online environment, a person can appear to others in the image they desire and easily change this identity. Due to anonymity and remote communication, the created identity can differ significantly from the real one or completely correspond to it. A person can resort to distortion of information, creating an image that meets their ideals and desires. As a result, they get the opportunity for self-realization and try out roles that are not available to them in real life. In this way, young people can experiment with different aspects of their self, which helps them understand their place in society.

At the same time, during adolescence, personal relationships and social environments play a key role in shaping one's per-

sonality. Online interactions with friends, followers, and other users are also important, which can influence self-esteem and self-perception. Access to a vast amount of information and resources on the Internet allows young people to find support and information that can greatly facilitate this process. Social networks and other resources are a place where teenagers share their ideas, get inspired, and create communities that support each other. In addition, digital technologies open up new horizons for education and self-expression. Using blogs, podcasts, and videos, people can develop their creativity and engage their audience. They become not only consumers but also producers of content, which strengthens their self-confidence and provides opportunities for self-expression.

Thus, «double growing up» can be a serious challenge, but on the other hand, it makes the younger generation more flexible, adaptive and ready for the upcoming difficulties. Conscious use of technology can be a key aspect in the formation of successful and self-confident people, capable of initiating positive changes both in their own lives and in society as a whole.

Secondly, the digital age is transforming the perception of space. A new reality has emerged in which physical distance is no longer relevant. People are becoming part of a global information field, where their opinions and ideas can be quickly shared around the world, opening up new horizons for collaboration and teamwork. In particular, video calling and online conferencing technologies make it possible to hold international meetings without the need for participants to be physically present. This approach reduces time costs and increases the availability of interactions between different cultures and communities. Technologies not only change the ways of communication, but also serve as catalysts for the creation of a new socio-cultural environment that supports and develops the potential of each of us. These changes reflect the essence of human nature and our constant need for connections and interactions, highlighting the importance of technology as a tool that, if used correctly,

can enrich our lives.

However, focusing on virtual interactions also brings with it a number of challenges: the need to rethink relationships that were previously based on physical presence and face-to-face communication, ethical and privacy issues, cyberbullying, and even emotional burnout [2; 6]. It is important to be mindful of how we use technology to make the most of new opportunities while still maintaining the ability to value emotional experiences and human connections.

Thirdly, modern technologies leave little time for reflection, creating a habit of acting quickly. Constant interactions, notifications, synchronous interfaces, intrusive information from social networks lead to the fact that people are physically present in one place, but mentally and emotionally somewhere else. Distractions do not allow people to focus on themselves. The mass flow of information creates the impression in people of the undoubted need to be constantly busy. There is a constant threat of being left out of the process. Unfortunately, modern youth faces a problem when in a world dominated by a culture of instant response, and everything is available at the touch of a button, they cannot always stop, reflect, engage in introspection. This leads to the inability to effectively manage their time, set priorities, and the lack of an internal resource for self-awareness.

However, despite the challenges people face in today's digital space, learning and consciously using technology provides access to unlimited opportunities for learning and self-expression, which can have a positive impact on personal development and the formation of social skills. Thus, they act as life assistants for a modern person.

Time management technologies (various scheduling apps) allow users to create to-do lists and set reminders. This not only helps with planning, but also with prioritization, allowing you to focus on the most important tasks. The ability to mark tasks as completed creates a sense of achievement and helps increase motivation. These digital tools can integrate with other platforms,

such as email and messaging, making it easier to communicate and receive real-time updates on upcoming tasks. All of this saves time and effort, which is especially valuable in an environment of rapid change and increased information volume. Research shows that people who use scheduling apps often report lower levels of stress and anxiety associated with organizing daily tasks [9].

Digital technologies are becoming increasingly important in the field of health and well-being. Devices such as fitness trackers and smart watches not only record data, but also analyze it, providing recommendations for improving lifestyle. Special apps remind users to move throughout the day, stretch, and take short breaks, and suggest exercises to improve well-being. Intrinsic motivation created by digital reminders and activity tracking can be an important factor in maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

Users can also set personalized goals, such as the number of steps they want to take per day or the total time spent physically active. These measures not only motivate people to take action, but also allow them to see the results of their efforts in real time. This can lead to more informed choices about nutrition, activity levels, and rest. In addition, these devices can track physiological indicators, allowing users to be more mindful of their own health. Monitoring nutrition, mental health, and sharing information with healthcare providers helps to develop a responsible approach to their own health and well-being, which ultimately leads to a better quality of life.

Modern digital tools also provide extensive opportunities for collaboration and project management. Team members can see who is responsible for what, which eliminates confusion and reduces the likelihood of duplication of efforts. Having a central platform where all project information is stored helps avoid misunderstandings and reduces the time spent searching for necessary data and documents. Such applications simplify communication between team members; create a more open and transparent work environment where everyone can

comfortably share ideas and suggestions. Importantly, this approach also helps increase employee motivation, as project participants can see the results of their efforts and demonstrate their contribution to the common goal.

In conclusion, digital technologies currently play a key role in transforming various aspects of life. Changing ways of communicating, using mobile devices and applications for time management, organizing work processes, motivating people to lead a healthy lifestyle, controlling their health, learning and self-expression open up unique

opportunities for personal growth and socialization. On the other hand, new technologies also challenge people, influencing the formation of real and online personal identity, contributing to the emergence of such problems as cyberbullying, decreased social activity in the real world and the impact of a constant flow of information on the emotional state. In this regard, it is important to change human consciousness, understanding the need to adopt technologies and the ability to integrate competently them into our lives.

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